

Absence of Islamic Studies in contemporary Educational System: An Analytical Analysis

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Abstract

A man is composed of soul and body. Without soul a man is called a dead body. Education is also a comprehensive term it nurtures soul and body at a time. The body is made by earth's material and soul came from sky so body would fulfil its requirement from earth whereas soul would get food from sky. By and large man is moving only around material and ignoring soul or spirit so fail to go ahead; man can send soft things around world within no time and a century was called IT's century whereas Asif bin Barkhiya who had the knowledge of sky book he brought a throne of Balqees in twinkling of an eye to the Holy Solomon PBUH (¹). The throne was thousands of miles far and hundreds of ton weighty. As the gap is found in IT so it is in totally contemporary education. Islamic study claims itself as a combination of all revealed knowledge which makes a complete growth of a man physically and spiritually. To include Islamic Study, it will be a comprehensive and inclusive in education which will lead man to his higher stage and the gap of spiritual growth in contemporary education would be bridged by Islamic studies.

Keywords: Man, soul, body, Islamic studies, contemporary education

1. Introduction

Every man of human being is thinking about something all time in his life. His thinking inspire him to act and sometime it goes to make some principles of his action. His that principles those make an indomitable will for action are really faith of that person. Religions bestow some perfect faiths by which man makes his practice perfectly. Infect practice of a person is really phenomena of his thinking and faiths. The function of education is to grow up man's thinking which should be accordance with his theological faiths for his proper and fruitful growth otherwise his thinking would be divided into two parts one religious thinking and second other than religious thinking. Contemporary education has no religious perspectives, it is out from some universal realities like a complete set-up of life of man and universe. In this development man look like at fixed condition or double minded. Especially in theological perspective education grow up a man's spiritual growth as well physically. Whereas Contemporary education has no space to spiritual growth so it become a big gape in Contemporary education that is why man is losing his perfect stage in this universe. Man didn't come in this world by his own will he has been coming from Adam by his Creator. Man will be asked for his practices of this life, so his life will be succeeded by the descended knowledge from his Creator. Contemporary education has a blankness of descended or revealed knowledge. In this study it will try to discuss about the gap and to bridge the gap through theological perception of education and specifically through Islamic Studies.

1.1. Objectives of Research

- To bridge the gap of spiritual growth in contemporary education.
- To potentiate mankind with the energy of spiritual powers on globe for better progress.
- To build a capability of students for acquiring their mentally calm as well as physically

1.2. Limitations

This study will remain in circle of perception of education specifically; positivism, scientific empiricism, by which contemporary education is impacted.

1.3. Research methodology

The research in its nature is qualitative and descriptive. For this reason books, theses, articles, were consulted for the collection of data. However the first and foremost sources were Quran and Sunnah for the analysis of data. They played the role of touchstone for checking the validity, and authenticity of data. They author also took some material from library after careful assurance and validation.

2. Theological Gape in Contemporary thinking

According to August Comte (²) the evolution of human intellectual has three stages, "From the study of human intelligence in all directions and through all times the discovery arises of a great fundamental law to which it is necessarily subject find which has a solid foundation of proof both in act of our organization and in our historical

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experiences the law is this, that each of our leading conceptions, each branch our knowledge passes successfully through different theoretical stages: first stage was theological stage, second stage was metaphysically stage and third stage is positive stage". (3)

Now man is going in the third stage which is also known as logical positivism or scientific empiricism. Contemporary education is drifting with pressure of this stage. According to dictionary of philosophy the positivism is as:

"For instance, defined positivism as a system that confined itself to data of an experience and did not include a relation to deductive or metaphysical beliefs". (4)

In the above passages it declared that gradually man was going far from religions that is not good for man Islamic scholars declare it a decline which was developed by Europe. Shah wali Allah (5) also describes some periods of European decline of thinking:

- Periods of Greek (Before plato and Aristotle),
- Periods of Roman (plato and Aristotle thinking),
- Periods of christen, (from 5th to 15th century)
- Periods of Renaissance (15th to start of 17th century),
- Periods of Rational (17th to 18th century),
- Periods of scarred thinking(19th century which is called modernism age), (6)

In the above periods, according to Shah Wali ullah; man was gradually attracted by materialistic thinking and arrived in the present age of modernization in this perception of positivism.

3. Atheistic and theistic thinking

Contemporary education based on scientific empiricism is a proof of atheistic thinking. Only observations and experiences are not sufficient to understand and to utilize these fineries of universe here is need for metaphysical and super nature along with physic and nature. Its proper way is hidden in theological perception of education and I can say in the perception of Islamic weltanschauung, in theistic perception we found a natural and comprehensive picture of universe. In the perception of Atheistic it doesn't remain wrong to throw bomb on people because they will have to die and it will have to do an experiment. Experiments are not a wrong way to use but its perception or context should be on base of realities. In scientific empiricism there is no space to acknowledge hereafter because we cannot get any experienced material from there. In theological perception this world is the biggest proof of hereafter if it is something openly exist here (this world) why it will not be hereafter? It may be said that positivism doesn't say anything against hereafter but the picture of life of a man is incomplete without have a faith in hereafter. Whereas in Islamic perception of throwing bomb, there remains an indication of hope because it admire the lives are connected with hereafter if anyone will do wrong he will be asked in hereafter. Psychologically Islamic perception of knowledge is very essential in this era. Epistemologically scientific empiricism is based on atheism it is need to purify it with theism. Theology imparts an education which based on realities and nature of man. It is understood reality that man and universe are made by someone. The creator of this cosmos is God all religions agreed about, though they gave different name of God but infect God is creator and He knows the best for every aspect of all his creation and His granted knowledge is most beneficial for man. Holy Quran says about:

اللَّهُ الَّذِي خَلَقَ سَبْعَ سَمَاوَاتٍ وَمِنَ الْأَرْضِ مِثْلَهُنَّ يَنْزِلُ الْأَمْرُ بَيْنَهُنَّ لِتَعْلَمُوا أَنَّ اللَّهَ عَلَىٰ كُلِّ شَيْءٍ قَدِيرٌ وَأَنَّ اللَّهَ قَدْ أَحَاطَ بِكُلِّ شَيْءٍ عِلْمًا (7)

"It is Allah (God) who has created seven heavens and of the earth the like thereof (i e seven). His command descends between them (heaven and earth) that you may know that Allah has power over all things, and that Allah surrounds all things in (His) knowledge." (8)

In this verse we are informed that the universe is made by God and He also gave the knowledge by which we can utilize this universe properly. The knowledge is along with man from his inception and will be up to end of man. Holy Quran is a book of creator of universe. As a company produce any product the company gives a catalogue book along with product, that book is the best for that product so universe has a catalogue book in the shape of Holy Quran. The above verse has the same sense that Holy book is an order of God co-related to seven heavens and of the earth. By ignoring this most precious knowledge education will remain unclear and a blankness and obviously a gape would be sighted in education until theistic thinking will not be included.

4. Spiritual gap and growth

Man has five senses like to see, to hear, to speak, to touch, and to taste. These are his appearing tools. Education is imparting by these and it improves the capacity of these senses. These are only overt senses of a man, whereas a man has his covert also. Contemporary education has no concerning to covert or disappearance of a man. According to Islamic education a man has his covert which also has senses like Rooh (soul), qulab (mind), sirr, Khafi, Ikhfa (hidden powers) those are also functioning in covert of a man like overt senses are functioning these are also most important for a man same as five census are important, these also require growth through education.(9)

Education grows a complete growth of an individual like physically and spiritually whereas contemporary education ignores spiritual growth that is why it occurs a big gape in education. Man stands very far from his real stage in this universe. To facilitate himself manmade houses to stay, cars/plains/ ships to travel, he made bomb to protect himself, these all things were existed from very long history of man like Egyptian pyramids can be see those are including in classical seven wonders of world. Infact man is ignoring half fragments of his body in contemporary education. According to maulana Ashra Ali thanvi (10):

“Man is combination of three fragments Body, soul and intellect. So it is categorically declared that education of a man in human being would be serviceable in keeping mind of these three fragments. In any aspect of education the requirement of these three or any one of three cannot ignore. If it would emphasize to only requirement of body in education and ignored soul and intellect then man would be like animal. If it would emphasize to only requirement of intellect then man would be suffered from satanic activities, he will go in useless debates etc. If it would emphasize to only requirement of soul then man would be loosed his potential to do his duties those duties are imposed on him by Society or religion”. (11)

In contemporary education, there is no classification of knowledge every knowledge is admired for man which is proven by experiment and observation whereas many knowledge may be wrong in collectively society. Like free sex is not admirable it may lead a man towards animal life. Spiritually man dislikes to go towards animal life. For this purpose contemporary education should be careful about his spreading knowledge as Shah Wali Ullah Says that epistemologically knowledge should be checked. For this checking Shah Wali Ullah introduced a term “Art of wisdom”.

5. Preface of knowledge

This term (art of wisdom) uses Shah wali ullah he says any knowledge which is taught should has coherence with other knowledge. How the knowledge will be fruitful for others? Isn't it in loss for others? He says this is an art of wisdom. These aspects should be kept in mind about when we are innovate new knowledge.

Topic of art of wisdom is: “as developed knowledge which should be personal beneficial and fruitful for public”. This art was introduced by Holy prophet Muhammad PBUH and some say that Plato introduced this art of wisdom at first.

Art of wisdom is the best art to check rational and irrational, advantaged and disadvantaged type of knowledge and easier to select proper books and the best teachers. A man cannot be completed except this knowledge. Many people have abundant knowledge but those remained deprive to get real advantages of knowledge which satisfied a man. (12)

Contemporary education doesn't care about the merits and demerits of knowledge neither it has any concerning with the spirit of man nor his ethics. These qualities can be empowered through religious education which based on revealed knowledge that knowledge has special concerning with spirit and soul of a person.

6. Islamic perception of education

Islam allows to learn every type of knowledge from every type of teacher. We can see the eve of War (ghazwa e Baddar) when the Holy prophet PBUH told to his companion (Sehaba) to learn from their directly enemies, those were prisoners. According to the sayings of Holy prophet PBUH;

كلمة الحكمة ضالة المؤمن يا خذها حيث وجدها (13)

“Rational is a legacy of Momin (Muslim); where he finds it, it is his own”

Islamic studies consist in faiths worships and affairs. Islamic education bases on faiths in monotheism, prophet hood, revealed books, angels and hereafter. If knowledge has any type of collision with these basic Islamic that never be fruitful for man. Educational Science is imparted in perception of Islamic weltanschauung. Islamic Affairs are of two kinds:

1. **Islamic lawfully affairs:** How we have to deal with ourselves and with mankind, it is categorically predicated in Islamic literature, which calls Islamic jurisprudence.

2. **Cosmic affairs:** How we have to utilize this cosmos. Holy Quran emphasizes to look at the universe and get lesson from this cosmos and challenges man to point out any type of insufficiency in it. (14)

Actually a man can get the most closeness of his God through to understand cosmic affairs. Contemporary Science is also innovating new knowledge about universe but its perception is not as like mystics adopt this way to get closeness of God. The universe is the witness of our disappeared God. We can find Allah SWT by searching Him in these cosmic affairs.

A mystic says;

“To have a faith in monotheism without any witness of monotheism is as if a person fell in a trench” (15).

This universe is full with witness of monotheism. This universe system is as vast that a person is unable to understand it we can only effort to understand it. Whereas we are more closing our tools to understand it by using the limit of experiment and observation, we should have to make it vast by using the spiritual tools then we will be able to understand

this universe better. Our target should be to acquire the knowledge of that person who brought the Bench of Balqees (Takhat e Balqees) with in no time by power of knowledge⁽¹⁶⁾.

It is a primary goal of education to try best to understand this universe,⁽¹⁷⁾ here we need especial ideology to understand it and Islam provides us that ideology which is called Islamic weltanschauung that; this cosmos is made by God and man is his substitute and he can understand this cosmic affairs in the light of Quran.

7. Broadness of Islamic studies

The most basic source of Islamic Study is the Holy Quran. When the Quran came it was the time there was no any technological approach to understand the solar system and its round but Quran said on that time that:

وَالشَّمْسُ تَجْرِي لِمُسْتَقَرٍّ لَهَا (18)

“Sun moves toward its destination”

Modern science never satisfies to its own statement, according to its principle it see doubtfully to all statements that is why man walk in round while Faith is the name of final and clear cut statement Islamic Study based on faith that every statement of Holy Quran is true and final let, us move ahead in the light of this statement. After the statement of movement of sun Quran says sun is subjected for men:

وَسَخَّرَ لَكُمُ اللَّيْلَ وَالنَّهَارَ وَالشَّمْسَ وَالْقَمَرَ وَالنُّجُومَ مُسَخَّرَاتٌ بِأَمْرِهِ إِنَّ فِي ذَلِكَ لآيَاتٍ لِقَوْمٍ يَعْلَمُونَ (19)

“And he has subjected to you the night and the day, and the sun and the moon; and the stars are subjected by his command. Surely in this are proofs for people who understand”.⁽²⁰⁾

Subjected is used in the translation of Arabic word TASKHEER which has sense to repress or have a control on something like when we are riding on horse we have a control on it. Man can control these all belongings of universe even day and night, and sun and moon, and stars are in control of a man by the order are command of Creator (God) of these things. In another time Quran says:

يَا مَعْشَرَ الْجِنِّ وَالْإِنسِ إِنِ اسْتَطَعْتُمْ أَنْ تَنْفُذُوا مِنْ أَقْطَارِ السَّمَاوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ فَانفُذُوا لَا تَنْفُذُونَ إِلَّا بِسُلْطَانٍ (21)

“Group of gents and men if you wish to cross this space you cannot cross except the power of its creator”.

Quran hundreds of years before had declared that if we shall try according to the rules and law of Almighty Allah we can cross space. We can control sea we can control sun, moon and even all galaxies moving in space. Those are not useless those are mad to serve the man, he should utilize it through reveled knowledge. Not only through rational knowledge. Ration was mad to understand revelation it is never and ever criterion, it need some directions it need some final and clear knowledge the criterion to go step forward. Now contemporary education considered intellect as a criterion and suffered from transgress, overestimation or proudness those are the symbols of failure. The first revelation message of God is pertain to “knowledge” and “education” first reveled word is “READ” (IQRA) and firstly told the all wisdoms of knowledge and was forbidden to adopt some basic status like don’t to be an overestimated when a man learn something he says himself self-sufficient which is poison, self is nothing, reality is revelation, real education is in revelation don’t be a self-sufficient. Holy book says:

عَلَّمَ الْإِنسَانَ مَا لَمْ يَعْلَمُ () كَلَّا إِنَّ الْإِنسَانَ لِرَبِّهِ لَكَنَاطٍ () أَنْ رَأَاهُ اسْتَعْجَى () إِنَّ إِلَىٰ رَبِّكَ الرُّجْعَى (22)

“Man knew what he didn’t know. Beware man may be go overestimated. He see himself as a self-sufficient. He has to go back toward his God”.

These verses are showing the gape of contemporary education. Man is unable to be criterion or self-sufficient because he is unable to see any single coming movement of his life. He has really a little knowledge his thinking level is very low he can a big loss in favor of little profit Islamic education has solid proof about little knowledge low level of thinking of man.⁽²³⁾ contemporary education is concern almost half side of men it did not discuss the reality of man that where he came and where he will have to go??? Contemporary education exempted itself from these realities by saying that those are belonged to religious education and contemporary education is mundane education. Education is a comprehensive word there is no space for any dichotri like religious and mundane. This dichotri or dualism is really gape and it can be bridged by religions.

Islamic Study emphasize on the growth of social academic, ethical, public and corporeal prospective. Islamic educational system has to increase the awareness of the man that he was emerging he is servant and worshiper of God. It is developed ones soul and heart by Islamic education.

This cosmos where we live and also are a part of it. It has some basic rules by which it is running these are the rules of universe those are instilled in it by its creator. When a man steps forward by spiritual knowledge and power then he knows some mysteries of universe. By his limited knowing he expose the mysteries or some mysteries are opened upon him to pick the weight of vicegerent of God. Man uses his basic tools; experiment and observation the acquire knowledge by these both tools is not final or total. Those are only branches of a big mystery. The result of the tools is not estimable as a final sometime this knowledge indicate us for the total and final result but as a whole these are not admirable. Here we see the importance of apostles and messengers of God those gave us the final and pragmatic knowledge to understand these cosmic affairs.⁽²⁴⁾ Holy Quran gives us a guideline to utilize the modern science, Allah says:

سُورِهِمْ آيَاتِنَا فِي الْأَفَاقِ وَفِي أَنْفُسِهِمْ حَتَّىٰ يَبَيِّنَ لَهُمُ اللَّهُ الْحَقُّ (25)

“We (ALLAH) shall show in near future keepsakes in man and universe”.

We should place the science as a covert of keepsakes of Allah SWT and never admit it as providence of men. This is an overall conception of science in Islamic ideology. We should utilize science in this conception through education.

Introduced education of science which is impressing us has a gape of misconception about ontology, metaphysics and super nature. This gape cannot bridge without Islamic thinking because there is a need for explicit the spirit whereas science is secular and moving in the circle of only matter. When it will be discussed spirit then as far as I am it will be the first day of men’s renaissance. Because our religion is the most basic requirement of a man.

8. Primary educational goals

Islamic educationists emphasis on roots of education that why education is imparted? They describe that education should be to achieve some basic goals. Basically a man should be a proper behavior holder, a good man, a good worshiper, a good citizen of country and globe. Two Muslim educationists say:

“Education should aim at the balanced growth of the total personality of man through the training of man’s spirit, intellect, his rational self, feelings and bodily senses. Education should cater therefore for the growth of man in all its aspects: spiritual, intellectual, imaginative, physical, scientific, linguistic, both individually and collectively and motivate all aspects towards goodness and the attainment of perfection. The ultimate aim of Muslim education lies in the realization of complete submission to Allah on the level of the individual, the community and humanity at large”.²⁶(

In other words we can say education is a process of receiving systematic instructions those bring up or nourish the abilities of individuals and help them to draw out their aims of lives, those aims are infect primary goals of education. Man has soul and body, both need for growth in the same time. This growth is an utmost and primary goal of education. Because education is imparted to generate a qualified, skillful and ethic full citizen on glob .The lesson to generate these qualities is hidden in Islamic studies whereas modern education ignored to adopt it that is why modern Education failed to achieve basic educational goals like spiritual growth of an individual. Contemporary education based on experiments and observations, those are insufficient tools to achieve the goals. Islamic studies comprise on Faiths, Worships and Affairs, these potentiate an individual to physical, spiritual and intuitive power those are likely to achieve the goals. For example; to try to understand the universe (cosmos) is a basic goal of education, which is easier to achieve by spiritual and intuitive power than only experiments and observations. Islamic study is an integrated, comprehensive and inclusive subject which comprise on sky knowledge and sufficient for complete growth of a man, it has an essence to achieve primary educational goals.

If it is ignored to achieve basic educational goals then education would remain useless. Contemporary education focused on secondary goals like to make a man as a Doctor, engineer or other skillful personality though it is an important need but until a person will not be a good man or good citizen his skill will not as fruitful so he would be after completion as a perfect man or citizen. ⁽²⁷⁾ If somewhere the basic step remains pending then secondary step will definitely go astray. So it is a dire need to epistemologically recheck of contemporary education in the light of religions and especially in the light of Islamic Study. it is not obligated to be a Muslim for the Study of Holy Quran this book addresses to man not only to Muslims So Man Should get benefit from the Book.

9. Conclusion and Findings

The man on glob is trying his best to utilize this universal resources but as this universe is serving human he could understand a little bit about, because of an improper perception of education. We found some results of this deficiency:

- Education is a comprehensive word there is no space of any type of dichotri like religious and mundane.
- The man needs a complete growth which will be done by comprehensive education.
- Contemporary education cannot make a complete growth of an individual without religious perception of education.
- Intellect is not a criterion it needs some guidelines to understand the realities. Through revealed knowledge ration can get the real rational stage.
- If it is made an effort today to understand the spirit of mater then it would be easy to send thing as it is sending today only soft things.

10. Recommendations (Please write few more recommendations)

- Curriculum of contemporary education needs for a diametrically change it should be developed in theological perception.
- Education should be based on the faiths specifically educational experiments and observations to be included in this perception.

- Educationists on the globe should deliver a complete picture of man and cosmos; why these were made and what will be their end? Lest it would prove that half knowledge is a curse.

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 (27) In western it is focused the word citizen whereas in Islamic world the word man is focused for basically to be made an individual by education, it would be out of touch to discuss it here, both words are very nearer and has nearly same sense. (writer)